

Phytochemical investigation of *Pleurotus ostreatus* : A novel medicinal mushroom

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Abstract : The present study deals with phytochemical examination of *Pleurotus ostreatus*, an important medicinal mushroom. Currently, medicinal beneficial effects of mushrooms are becoming progressively recognized and have fascinated much attention in their application in food and pharmaceuticals. This study involves the preliminary phytochemical screening and identification of compounds which were present in crude ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* by standard methods. Further, GC-MS analysis of the crude ethanolic extract has been studied. The qualitative analysis of the ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, phenols, carbohydrates and proteins. Consequently the preliminary survey of the scan showed that the ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* confirmed by spectrum analysis. These results suggest that the photochemical properties of the *P. ostreatus* were responsible for curing various diseases. Owing to the presence of these phytochemicals, *P. ostreatus* mushroom acts as a novel source of various types of bioactive compounds with diverse chemical structures as well as pharmacological activities.

Keywords : *Pleurotus ostreatus*, phytoconstituent, GC-MS, antioxidant.

Introduction

The inexorable use of synthetic termiticides is a major threat to the natural environment, and as a result there is an urgent need to investigate and consume naturally occurring products for combating harmful termites¹. Historically, mushrooms are well known for their various bioactivities. The pharmacological value of the plant lie in some active chemical substances called phytochemical that produce a physiological action on the human body. Phytochemicals are naturally occurring biochemical compounds in plants for colour, flavour, smell and for defence mechanism against predation by many microorganisms, insects and herbivores². It has been shown that *in vitro* screening methods could provide the necessary preliminary clarification to select crude plant extracts with potentially useful properties for further chemical and pharmacological investigations³. Owing to the development of hyphenated chromatographic techniques such as GC or LC-MS can analysis the phytoconstituents in plants⁴.

The bioaccumulation potential of nutrients in fungal mycelium enriched with essential elements for human health has been investigated in mushroom⁵. *P. ostreatus*

is the second most important cultivated mushroom for food purposes throughout worldwide⁶. Nutritionally, it has unique flavour and aromatic properties and it is considered to be rich in protein, fibre, carbohydrates, minerals and vitamins as well as low fat^{7,8}. Nowadays, research has tended to spotlight on the dietary values of edible mushrooms; however there is little information pending about their phytoconstituents. However, taking into consideration of the medicinal consequence of this mushroom *P. ostreatus* was analysed qualitatively and quantitatively by GC-MS techniques. This study will be helpful to identify the compounds of therapeutic value. GC-MS is one of the paramount techniques to identify the bioactive constituents with long chain, branched chain hydrocarbons, alcohols, acids and ester etc.

Experimental

Material :

P. ostreatus mushrooms were collected in and around areas of Uthagamandalam, Nilagiri district, Tamilnadu. The plant was taxonomically identified and authenticated by Dr. V. Venkatesalu, Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Annamalai University. A voucher specimen

(No. 233) was deposited at the herbarium of Botany, Department of Botany, Annamalai University.

Ethanollic extract :

The fresh fruiting bodies of *P. ostreatus* were dried in shade conditions and the dried materials were pulverized in a blender to get coarse powder. For *P. ostreatus* fruiting bodies ethanolic extraction, five grams of the powder was extracted with 100 mL of 95% ethanol using a soxhlet apparatus. The last trace of solvent was removed under reduced pressure distillation and then vacuum dried. The dried crude ethanolic extract of the *P. ostreatus* has been used for the GC-MS analysis.

Preliminary phytochemical screening :

The preliminary phytochemical screening was carried out by following standard methodologies to screen out the specific identities^{24,25}. The extract was subjected to screen out the presence of various bio-active phyto-constituents.

Determination of alkaloids :

5 mL of the extract was added to 2 mL of HCl. To this acidic medium, 1 mL of Dragendroff's reagent was added. A red orange precipitate produced which indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Determination of steroids :

1 mL of the extracts was dissolved in 10 mL of chloroform and equal volume of concentration sulphuric acid was added by sides of the test tube. The upper layer turns red and sulphuric acid layer showed yellow with green fluorescence. This indicates the presence of steroids.

Determination of terpenoids :

5 mL of ethanolic extract is mixed with 2 mL of CHCl_3 in a test tube. 3 mL of concentration H_2SO_4 was carefully added to the mixture to form a layer. An interface with a reddish brown coloration was formed which indicates the presence of terpenoids.

Determination of flavanoids :

A few drops of 1% NH_3 solution is added to the ethanolic extract in a test tube. A yellow coloration was observed which showed the presence of flavonoid.

Determination of tannins :

The 0.5 g of sample of extract is boiled in 20 mL of distilled water in a test tube and then filtered. The filtra-

tion method used here is the normal method, which includes a conical flask and filter paper. The 0.1% FeCl_3 is added to the filtered sample and observed for brownish green or a blue black coloration, which shows the presence of tannins.

Determination of phenols :

The extract of 50 mg was dissolved in 5 mL of distilled water. To this few drops of neutral ferric chloride solution was added and observed for a dark green coloration²⁶.

Determination of proteins :

To a small amount of ethanolic extract, 5–6 drops of Million's reagent was added. A white precipitate which turns red on heating was formed and it indicates the presence of proteins.

Determination of carbohydrates :

To 0.5 mL of filtrate 0.5 mL of Benedict's reagent was added. The mixture was heated on a boiling waterbath for 2 min and after that observed for characteristic red colored precipitate formation (Benedict's test).

Thin layer chromatography :

Two microliter of sample was applied on precoated silica gel of 60 F₂₅₄ aluminium plates (MERK, 7 × 1.5 cm size). Develop the plate in hexane : ethyl acetate (7 : 3) mobile phase.

GC-MS analysis :

GC-MS analysis was carried out on a (GC Clarus 500) Perkin-Elmer GC used in this analysis employed a fused silica column packed with Elite-5MS [5% diphenyl/95% dimethyl poly siloxane, 30 nm × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm df] and the components were separated using helium as carrier gas at a constant flow of 1 mL/min. The 2 μL sample extract injected into the instrument was detected by the turbo gold mass detector (Perkin-Elmer) with the aid of the turbo mass 5.2 software. During the 36th min GC extraction process, the oven was maintained at a temperature which was set at 250 °C (mass analyser). The different parameters involved in the operation of the Clarus 500 MS, were also standardized (Inlet line and source temperature : 200 °C). Mass spectra were taken at 70 eV a scan interval of 0.5 s and fragments from 45 to 450 Da. The MS detection was completed in 36 min.

Identification of components :

Interpretation of mass spectrum GC-MS was conducted using the database of NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology), WILEY8 and FAME having more than 65000 patterns. The spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the known components stored in the NIST08. LIB, WILEY8. LIB (MC Lafferty) and FAME. LIB library (Stein SE). The name, molecular weight and structure of the components of the test materials were ascertained. The relative percentage amount of each component was calculated by comparing its average peak area to the total area. Software adopted to handle mass spectra and chromatograms was a GC-MS solution ver 2.53.

Results and discussion

The diet taken by human includes plenty of different fruits, vegetables, mushrooms and other plant products which ensure ingestion of various phytochemicals throughout life. More recently researchers have been increased exposure to require for biologically active compounds with low profiles of adverse reactions compared to pharmacological drug. This has triggered an extensive investigation of herbal phytochemicals and their mechanism of actions⁹. The standard phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of alkaloid, steroid, terpenoids, tannins, phenols, proteins and carbohydrates in the *P. ostreatus*. And flavanoids are absence in ethanolic extract. The results were documented in Table 1. These compounds acquire a wide spectrum of chemical and biological activities including radical scavenging properties, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial properties, etc.

Table 1. Phytochemical analysis of ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus*

Phytochemicals	Inference
Alkaloids	+
Steroids	+
Terpenoids	+
Flavanoids	-
Tannins	+
Phenols	+
Proteins	+
Carbohydrates	+

(+) Presence, (-) Absence.

Tannins are reacting with proteins to provide the typical tanning effect which is important for the treatment of inflammation (or) ulcerated tissues and they have remarkable activity in cancer prevention. Hence it may help in healing of wounds¹⁰. Terpenoids are believed to be active against cancer by enzymatically promoting glutathione transferase¹¹. These observations therefore support the use of *P. ostreatus* in herbal cure remedies. Another secondary metabolite observed in *P. ostreatus* was alkaloids. One of the most common biological properties of alkaloids is their toxicity against cells of foreign organisms. Hence it prevents DNA synthesis through inhibition of topoisomerase and it can act as antibacterial and antiviral substance¹². Steroidal compounds present in *P. ostreatus* extract are of important and interest due to their relationship with various anabolic hormones having similar structure of cholesterol which includes beta sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol. This reduces the risk factors of colon cancer¹³.

Phenolic compounds have been reported to be the major antioxidant component found in mushrooms. Hence, the phenolic content of *P. ostreatus* might account for antioxidant and scavenging agent against free radicals coupled with oxidative damage. The presence of phenol in extract may give credence to its local usage for the management of oxidative stress induced ailments¹⁴. Proteins contributed to the structure and functions of the living cells, they occur as independent units as well as in combination with lipids, nucleic acids, carbohydrates and several other compounds¹⁵. The presence of proteins indicates that the *P. ostreatus* may aid in growth, tissue repair and energy production in the body¹⁶. Carbohydrates are classified as sugars (mono and oligosaccharides) and polysaccharides¹⁷. Among the polysaccharides the mushroom cell wall are rich in non-starch polysaccharide (β -D-glucan) which is the most interesting functional components with strong antioxidant activity and anti-cancer activity¹⁸.

GC-MS analysis is the primary step towards understanding the nature of the active principle in their medicinal plants and mushrooms. And this type of study will be helpful for further detailed phytochemical study. Based on the GC-MS results, sixteen phytochemical constituents have been identified from the ethanolic extract of the *P. ostreatus*. The biological activities of phytochemicals constituents were prediction by the Duke's databases. The results pertaining to GC-MS analysis leads to the identification of numeral compounds from the GC fractions of the ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus*. These compounds

were recognized through mass spectrometry attached with GC. About sixteen peaks were identified in *P. ostreatus* by GC-MS analysis (Fig. 1). The active principles with their retention time (RT), molecular formula (MF), molecular weight (MW) and concentration (%) were presented in Table 2.

The prevailing compounds were undec-10-ynoic acid (23.81%) followed by methoxy acetic acid, 3-tridecyl ester (11.56%); octadecane, 6-methyl- (10.81%); 1-iodo-2-methylundecane (9.08%); decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl- (8.63%); 3-hexadecyloxycarbonyl-5-(2-hydroxyethyl) methylimidazolium ion (8.21%); decanoic acid, ethyl es-

Fig. 1. GC-MS chromatogram of ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus*.

Table 2. Phytochemical analysis of ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus*

No.	RT	Name of the compound	Molecular formula	Mol. wt.	Peak area (%)
1.	13.17	Decanoic acid, ethyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200	6.44
2.	14.28	Nonanoic acid	C ₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	158	1.11
3.	14.99	Undec-10-ynoic acid	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₂	182	23.81
4.	16.57	Hexadecanoic acid, 2-oxo-, methyl ester	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O ₃	284	1.98
5.	17.88	Valeric acid, 4-tridecyl ester	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284	4.99
6.	18.28	Cyclopentaneundecanoic acid	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂	254	0.74
7.	19.28	1-Iodo-2-methylundecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ I	296	9.08
8.	20.36	cis-9,10-Epoxyoctadecan-1-ol	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284	0.91
9.	20.70	Methoxyacetic acid, 3-tridecyl ester	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₃	272	11.56
10.	22.12	Octadecane, 6-methyl-	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268	10.81
11.	23.51	Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl-	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198	8.63
12.	24.20	5-Hexen-3-ol, 3-methyl-	C ₇ H ₁₄ O	114	1.44
13.	24.85	3-Hexadecyloxycarbonyl-5-(2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methylimidazolium ion	C ₂₄ H ₄₅ N ₂ O ₃	409	8.21
14.	26.20	6,10-Dimethyl-4-undecanol	C ₁₃ H ₂₈ O	200	4.42
15.	27.52	Octanal, 7-methoxy-3,7-dimethyl-(methoxycitronellal)	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ O ₂	186	5.45
16.	29.00	D-Mannotetradecane-1,2,3,4,5-pentaol	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O ₅	278	0.41

*Parameters tested are not covered under the scope of NABL accreditation.

Table 3. Activity of phytochemicals identified in the ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* by GC-MS

Sr. no.	Name of the compound	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Compound nature	Activities ^a
1.	Decanoic acid, ethyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200	Ester compound	Nematicide pesticide
2.	Nonanoic acid (or) Pelargonic acid	C ₉ H ₁₈ O ₂	158	Carboxylic acid	Flavor, FEMA 1-15, Perfumery
3.	1-Iodo-2-methylundecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ I	296	Iodo compound	Antifungal, antioxidant and antimicrobial agents, insecticidal
4.	Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl-	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	198	Alkane compound	No activity reported
5.	3-Hexadecyloxy carbonyl-5-(2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methylimidazolium ion	C ₂₄ H ₄₅ N ₂ O ₃	409	Amino compound	Antimicrobial
6.	Octadecane, 6-methyl-	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268	Alkane compound	No activity reported

^aSource : Dr. Duke's phytochemical and ethnobotanical database.

ter (6.44%); octanal, 7-methoxy-3,7-dimethyl-(methoxycitronellal) (5.45%); valeric acid, 4-tridecyl ester (4.99%); 6,10-dimethyl-4-undecanol (4.42%); hexadecanoic acid, 2-oxo-, methyl ester (1.98%); 5-hexen-3-ol, 3-methyl- (1.44%); nonanoic acid (1.11%); *cis*-9,10-epoxyoctadecane-1-ol (0.91%); cyclopentaneundecanoic acid (0.74%) and D-mannotetradecane-1,2,3,4,5-pentanol (0.41%).

The biological activities of some phytochemicals detected based on Dr. Duke's phytochemical and ethnobotanical databases by Dr. Jim Duke of the Agricultural Research Service/USDA were listed in Table 3. Some of the phytoconstituents like decanoic acid, ethyl ester (6.44%) were reported to possess nematicide and pesticide activities¹⁹. The compound nonanoic acid (pelargonic acid) (1.11%) exhibit flavor FEMA1-15, perfumery activity. Shahnaz Bakhtawar reported that nonanoic acid also predicted in GC-MS analyses of *Withania coagulans*²⁰.

Furthermore, 1-iodo-2-methylundecane (9.08%) possess antifungal, antioxidant, antimicrobial and insecticidal activities^{21,22}. However the amino compound named as 3-hexadecyloxy carbonyl-5-(2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methylimidazolium ion (8.21%) possesses antimicrobial activity²³. Where as alkane compounds like decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl- (8.63%) and octadecane, 6-methyl- (10.81%) had no activity which was conformed from Dr. Duke's phytochemical and ethnobotanical database. Out

of these sixteen bioactive constituents undec-10-ynoic acid (23.81%) was present in high quantity and D-mannotetradecane-1,2,3,4,5-pentaol (0.4%) was present in less quantity, and the other constituents were present in considerable amount.

By interpreting these compounds, it is found that *P. ostreatus* possess various salutary applications. The gas chromatogram shows the relative concentrations of various compounds getting eluted as a function of retention time. The height of the peak indicates the relative concentrations of the components present in *P. ostreatus*. Therefore the investigation concluded that presence of this compounds as shown in the study could contribute synergistically to the significant nutraceutical potency of *P. ostreatus* as well as the stronger extraction capacity of ethanol could have fashioned number of active constituents responsible for many biological activities.

Conclusion

In the present study the several phytochemicals in ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* were qualitatively analysed which includes alkaloid, steroid, terpenoids, tannins, phenols, proteins and carbohydrates. All totally sixteen phytochemical constituents have been identified by GC-MS analysis. Among the compound analysed iodo compounds have been known as antioxidant agents, which act as free radical terminators and have shown medicinal activity as well as exhibits physiological functions. Furthermore, amino compound act as antimicrobial agent and

ester compound posses nematocide and pesticide activity. Hence we can conclude that various bioactive compounds present in ethanoic extract of *P. ostreatus* have some imperative pharamacoligical properties. Even though further studies which includes isolation, purification and structure determination of chemical constituent responsible for these biological activities was inevitable to understand its detailed therapeutic application.

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